

Spatio-temporal Analysis of Manufacturing Industries in Gujarat

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Introduction & Need for Study

Industrialization has been understood to be as one of the key drivers for economic development. Industries have been envisaged as not only as the harbinger of economic growth, but are also viewed as means to reduce regional disparity. The thrust of the industrial development corporations of Gujarat has been to plan and implement industrial estates in backward regions to achieve economic and social development. With the liberalization of state policy, there is a radical change in the approach of the state towards industries. Industrialists are being sought after by the state functionaries to fetch investment in their regions.

During 1980, 1985, 2009, 2015 the State Government of Gujarat had declared various industrial policies with a package of fiscal incentives for small, medium & large-scale industries. By this policy State Government of Gujarat wants to attract industries in the state. However, despite giving attractive incentives, very few areas really develop industrially. The incentives are given all over the places but they are effective in only some areas; while the other areas remain as industrially backward as they were before incentive period. That suggests that there are other important factors related to industrial development and policies do not address these issues. So, through spatiotemporal analysis, it is important to identify the annual/decadal growth of industries in Gujarat and co-relate it to national and state-level policies to assess the relationship between the two.

This research would commence with broad overview of manufacturing industries in Gujarat and policies affecting their growth in different parts of the state. Post-Independence with the commencement of five-year plans and other industrial development policies by the national and state governments, manufacturing industries have been set up all over Gujarat with some major manufacturing hubs. Over the period of time, manufacturing industries have been set up in various places across the state based on factors such as provision of proper infrastructure, skilled or cheap labor force, accessibility to ports, SEZs, SIRs etc. to name a few.

Methodology & Analysis

The aim of this research is to understand the growth pattern of manufacturing industries in Gujarat through spatiotemporal analysis, i.e., based on type, location and period. Also it is important to understand how has the manufacturing industries in Gujarat evolved over the period of space and time and which specific kinds of manufacturing industries have come up and where they have been located.

The growth of open data is shifting the emphasis from longer term strategic planning to short-term thinking about how cities function and can be managed. Open data holds the promise of a rich, detailed and timely data that can provide a better understanding of complex problems of the world we live in. To study and identify the evolution of these industries, spatiotemporal analysis will be done based on data available from Ministry of Corporate Affairs, released under National Data Sharing and Accessibility Policy (NDSAP). So, the spatial data will be geo-coded and merged with non-spatial data of the large scale and MSME manufacturing industries in terms of type, location and period. It shall generate development trends, growth patterns and issues related to these industries. Out of the 81000 registered companies in Gujarat with Registrar of Companies* (as of 31.03.2015), more than 34000 are manufacturing industries of food, leather products, machinery and equipment, metal and chemicals, paper, textiles and wood products. These manufacturing industries are being considered for this study.

Type of Industry	Number of Industries
Metal & Chemical	14027
Textiles	7526
Machinery & Equipment	7203
Food Based	2315
Paper Based	1193
Wood Based	400
Leather Based	76
Others	1776
TOTAL	34509

After highlighting key findings and deriving conclusions, the research tends to focus on whether policies get implemented on ground and are cohesive with reality. This will enable planners and policy makers to utilize large databases over the period of space and time and assess the impacts of their policies. Regional planning strategies and policy recommendations can be derived using similar methodology. The research aims to provide a platform for urban and regional planners to implement and facilitates them to take urban and regional planning decisions based on evidence based planning.

**To carry out the spatiotemporal analysis, location of industries is very important. Hence, industries registered with Registrar of Companies (RoC) in the Ministry of Corporate Affairs has only been considered since their addresses are available. To further classify, only manufacturing industries are studied.*

Key Findings

- Despite liberalization of Indian economy in the early 1990s, concentration of manufacturing industries took place near large metropolises.
- The notion of decentralization of new industries and spreading of industries across various talukas of Gujarat hasn't achieved much of a success.
- Out of the 248 talukas in Gujarat, more than 66% of manufacturing industries are located in 3 talukas: Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Surat, thus reflecting the concentration of industries near market and metropolis.
- This also shows that other factors like Delhi Mumbai Industrial Corridor (DMIC), Dedicated Freight Corridor (DFC), National Highway-8, and locations of SIRs, SEZs, GIDCs have played a major role in concentrating manufacturing industries along Ahmedabad-Vadodara-Surat corridor.
- The graph showing the growth of manufacturing industries in Gujarat is an S-curve, thereby showing a rapid, exponential increase of manufacturing industries post-liberalization from 1991-1995 and 1996-2000, later due to state policies and promotion of industries from 2001-2005 and 2006-2010, followed by a tapering/leveling-off from 2011 onwards.
- Through the use of similar open data, spatial growth patterns of various sectors can be identified and analyzing the policy interventions can be done for better decision-making to take place.

CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1. Introduction

1.1 Introduction

Industrialization has been understood to be as one of the key drivers for economic development. Industries have been envisaged as not only as the harbinger of economic growth, but are also viewed as means to reduce regional disparity. The thrust of the industrial development corporations of Gujarat has been to plan and implement industrial estates in backward regions to achieve economic and social development.

Gujarat has always heavily depended up on industries for its economy because of poor agriculture facilities. Gujarat State was formed in the year 1960, since then it has done well in terms of overall economic growth. It has progressed to acquire the fourth rank in per capita income among the major sixteen States in India and has maintained this rank since last two decades. The favourable policies of the state government as well as the enterprising population of the state pushed the industrial sector up over the years with the result that the state is at the forefront of industrial development in the country today. Setting up of four important corporations, namely, GIIC (Gujarat Industrial Investment Corporation), GIDC, GSFC (Gujarat State Finance Corporation) and iNDEXTb (Industrial Extension Bureau) also boosted the industrial growth in the state by providing finance and other infrastructure facilities to the entrepreneurs. This approach has given rich dividends in terms of attracting industrial investments to the state, particularly in the large and medium industries.

With the liberalization of state policy, there is a radical change in the approach of the state towards industries. Industrialists are being sought after by the state functionaries to fetch investment in their regions. The cities of the world, are competing for attracting investments to their region, the Indian counterparts are not far off, with the ambitious state governments playing an important role.

1.2 Need of Study

It is coming across that Gujarat has successfully carved out a formidable position in industrial and manufacturing sector together with service sector. However the main drawback of the Gujarat model is its negligible performance in agricultural sector and regional imbalance in development. The fruits of high growth rate and development are limited to the mainland Gujarat. The tribal region of south and north Gujarat is lagging behind other parts in terms of economic and industrial development. The enterprising and commercial mind set in Gujarat has brought the state a forerunner in economic development. The state has not only acquired and maintained its fourth rank in per capita NSDP, but it has also taken quantum jump in the post liberalization period by attracting highest industrial development. The progress in economic diversification however doesn't seem to be sustainable as the primary sector has lagged far behind distorting the agriculture industry linkages. Gujarat needs to broaden the base of development through environment friendly and employment intensive development path. Only an inclusive model can make economic growth and development sustainable.

During 1980, 1985, 2009, 2015 the State Government of Gujarat had declared various industrial policies with a package of fiscal incentives for small, medium & large-scale industries. By this policy State Government of Gujarat wants to attract industries in the state. However, despite giving attractive incentives, very few areas really develop industrially. The incentives are given all over the places but they are effective in only some areas; while the other areas remain as industrially backward as they were before incentive period. That suggests that there are other important factors related to industrial development and policies do not address these issues. So, through spatiotemporal analysis, it is important to identify the annual/decadal growth of industries in Gujarat and co-relate it to national and state-level policies to assess the relationship between the two.

1.3 Aim

To understand the growth pattern of manufacturing industries in Gujarat through spatiotemporal analysis

1.4 Research Objectives

- To analyze the growth of manufacturing industries in Gujarat based on type, location and period

1.5 Research Questions

- How have the manufacturing industries in Gujarat evolved over the period of space and time?
- Which specific kinds of manufacturing industries have come up and where they have been located?

1.6 Methodology

This research would commence with broad overview of manufacturing industries in Gujarat and policies affecting their growth in different parts of the state. Post-Independence with the commencement of five-year plans and other industrial development policies by the national and state governments, manufacturing industries have been set up all over Gujarat with some major manufacturing hubs. Over the period of time, manufacturing industries have been set up in various places across the state based on factors such as provision of proper infrastructure, skilled or cheap labor force, accessibility to ports, SEZs, SIRs etc. to name a few.

Figure 1-1 Methodology

Registrars of Companies (ROC) appointed under Section 609 of the Companies Act covering the various States and Union Territories are vested with the primary duty of registering companies and LLPs floated in the respective states and the Union Territories and ensuring that such companies and LLPs comply with statutory requirements under the Act. These offices function as registry of records, relating to the companies registered with them. Out of the 81000 registered companies in Gujarat with Registrar of Companies (as of 31.03.2015), more than 34000 are manufacturing industries of food, leather products, machinery and equipment, metal and chemicals, paper, textiles and wood products. To analyze such database over the period of space and time, and to identify patterns and correlations, geo-spatial analysis becomes apparent.

Figure 1-2 Spatio-temporal analysis method

To study and identify the evolution of these industries, spatiotemporal analysis will be done based on data available from Ministry of Corporate Affairs, released under National

Data Sharing and Accessibility Policy (NDSAP). So, the spatial data will be geo-coded and merged with non-spatial data of the large scale and MSME manufacturing industries in terms of type, location and period. It shall generate development trends, growth patterns and issues related to these industries.

Figure 1-3 Relation between dependent and independent variables

After highlighting key findings and deriving conclusions, the research tends to focus on whether policies get implemented on ground and are cohesive with reality. This will enable planners and policy makers to utilize large databases over the period of space and time and assess the impacts of their policies. Regional planning strategies and policy recommendations can be derived using similar methodology. The research aims to provide a platform for urban and regional planners to implement and facilitates them to take urban and regional planning decisions based on evidence based planning.

1.7 Scope & Limitations

Through spatiotemporal analysis, we can identify growth pattern and key trends related to industries in Gujarat. This research tends to analyze the findings and co-relate them with policies for industrial growth.

To carry out the spatiotemporal analysis, location of industries is very important. Hence, industries registered with Registrar of Companies (RoC) in the Ministry of Corporate Affairs has only been considered since their addresses are available. To further classify, only manufacturing industries are studied.

CHAPTER 2
LITERATURE AND POLICY REVIEW

2. Literature and Policy Review

2.1 Introduction

After autonomy, industrialization was seen as the way to easing destitution. Industrialization not just guaranteed independence for its country that had quite recently recovered political power, additionally offered outer economies accumulating from specialized advancement. Trusting the capability of farming and fares to be restricted, Indian governments burdened horticulture by skewing the terms of exchange against it and underscoring import substitution, therefore offering need to substantial industry. The Industries Development and Regulation Act (IDRA) in 1951 established the frameworks for this regulatory control on mechanical limit. Be that as it may, after some time, the permitting necessities turned out to be progressively stringent and were joined by a range of methods and clearances. India's intercession in modern advancement has been broad. Dissimilar to numerous East Asian nations, which utilized their intercession to construct solid private part commercial ventures, India settled on regulatory control over key businesses. At various times, nationalized businesses included chemicals, electric force, steel, transportation, disaster protection, parts of the coal and material commercial enterprises and managing an account (Awasthi, 32). To advance these commercial enterprises the administration not just required high taxes and forced import confinements, additionally financed the nationalized firms, guided speculation assets to them, and controlled both area use and numerous costs.

Under Prime Minister Indira Gandhi (1966-77), two noteworthy movements occurred. To start with, the disregard of farming was turned around through state activism in financing new seeds and manures, horticultural credit, and country zap. The green transformation took off and by the mid-1970s India was independent in grain. The second move was the further fixing control over each part of the economy. Banks were nationalized, exchange was progressively limited, value controls were forced on an extensive variety of items, and outside speculation was crushed. In 1973, dealings in outside trades and in addition remote speculation came to be directed by the Foreign Exchange and Regulation Act (FERA). The demonstration for all intents and purposes close out the inflow of new innovation

from abroad in the 1970s and 1980s, especially when these included expansive value interest. Indian government went a long ways past the standard internal looking industrialization strategies that most creating nations sought after World War II. The legislature controlled the most fundamental business choices for all organizations over a specific size: getting, venture, limit use, evaluating and conveyance.

The over-prohibitive, and frequently self-overcoming nature of the administrative system started to wind up apparent by the late 1960s and mid 1970s. Extensive arranging was progressively condemned as arranged targets were not met and numerous arrangements were not in any case executed. The absence of achievement in a few measurements prompted another and more prohibitive arrangement of regulations. One illustration is the endeavor to save areas for little commercial ventures and to limit the development of expansive firms. (Menon, 102)

Starting in the mid 1980s, a gentle pattern towards deregulation began. Monetary changes were presented, beginning to change exchange, mechanical and budgetary approaches, while appropriations, charge concessions, and the devaluation of the money enhanced fare motivations. These measures helped GDP development to quicken to more than 5% every year amid the 1980s, contrasted with 3.5% amid the 1970s, and decreased neediness all the more quickly. However India's most basic auxiliary issues were just incompletely tended to. Charges kept on being among the most astounding on the planet, and quantitative limitations stayed pervasive. Besides, a noteworthy government impact proceeded in the allotment of credit to firms and a debilitation of remote speculation. Moderately wasteful open ventures, controlling almost 20% of GDP, remained a delay financial development.

The administration extended antipoverty plans, particularly rustic business plans, yet just a little division of the rising appropriations really achieved poor people. Rivalry between political gatherings drove endowments up at each decision. The subsequent monetary shortages (8.4% of GDP in 1985) added to a rising current record shortfall. India's remote trade stores were for all intents and purposes depleted by mid-1991 when another government headed by Narasimha Rao came to control. In July 1991, India dispatched a

second major financial change program. The legislature conferred itself to advancing a focused economy that would be interested in exchange and remote speculation. Measures were acquainted with decrease the administration's impact in corporate speculation choices. A great part of the mechanical permitting framework was disassembled, and regions once shut to the private area were opened up. These included power era, territories of the oil business, substantial industry, air transport, streets and a few information transfers. Outside speculation was abruptly invited.

More noteworthy worldwide mix was empowered with a critical lessening in the utilization of import licenses and taxes (down to 150% from 400%), an end of appropriations for fares, and the presentation of an outside trade market. Since April 1992, there has been no compelling reason to get any permit or allow to complete import-send out exchange. As of April 1, 1993, exchange is totally free, excepting just a little rundown of imports and fares that are either controlled or banned. The WTO evaluated a normal import tax of 71% in 1993, which has been decreased to 40% in 1995. With progressive extra financial changes, the rupee, since 1995, can almost be viewed as a completely convertible coin at business sector rates. India now has an a great deal more open economy.

2.2 Industrial Development in Gujarat

In this sort of a situation, since its development, Gujarat has dependably vigorously depended up on commercial ventures for its economy on account of poor agribusiness offices. Gujarat State was shaped in the year 1960, from that point forward it has done well as far as general monetary development. It has advanced to obtain the fourth rank in per capita pay among the real sixteen States in India and has kept up this rank since most recent two decades. Today it is one of the prosperous conditions of India with around 50 million populace (2001 evaluation) spread more than 196000 sq. km. The State has under 5 % (4.92%) of the national populace; it has 6.56 % of the national generation and around 16% of the national modern yield. Gujarat is among the most industrialized states in India, the modern division has performed reliably well with the development rate of the assembling segment persistently expanding from 3.04% in the sixties, to 5.55% in the

seventies, 8.73 % in the eighties, 11.92 % in the nineties and 16% in the most recent decade. Gujarat economy has experienced a noteworthy basic change amid the previous couple of decades and encountered a high rate of development of its NSDP. In any case, this can't be considered as attractive in light of the fact that the essential segment and especially horticulture has fallen a long ways behind with practically stagnant long haul development since the eighties.

The positive approaches of the state government and additionally the venturesome populace of the state pushed the mechanical segment up throughout the years with the outcome that the state is at the front line of modern advancement in the nation today. Setting up of four critical organizations, to be specific, GIIC (Gujarat Industrial Investment Corporation), GIDC, GSFC (Gujarat State Finance Corporation) and iNDEXTb (Industrial Extension Bureau) additionally supported the mechanical development in the state by giving fund and other foundation offices to the business people. The procedure of industrialization in Gujarat has taken another turn following the presentation of the financial changes in 1991. After the Government of India reported the NIP (New Industrial Policy) in 1991 with the goal of executing the monetary changes in the modern segment, Government of Gujarat has likewise reacted positively and declared its own particular mechanical arrangements. The administration has concocted a liberal bundle of concessions and motivators thusly over duty, deals charge on entire extent merchandise, for example, crude materials, moderate products, pressing materials, preparing materials, consumable merchandise, by items, scrap and waste materials and so forth. Moreover, there is transport sponsorship and capital speculation appropriation on countless. Alongside the sponsorships and concessions administration of Gujarat has given a high need to the advancement of base in the state. The legislature has set up Gujarat Infrastructure Development Board (GIDB) in 1995 with the targets of redesigning state framework. This methodology has given rich profits as far as drawing in mechanical speculations to the state, especially in the expansive and medium commercial enterprises.

2.2.1 Industries in Gujarat

Gujarat has recorded noteworthy financial improvement and is the most industrialized

condition of India. Taking after the alluring direct impetuses, Gujarat has seen full hailed modern improvement 1960 onwards. The condition of Gujarat is isolated into five zones viz. Focal Gujarat, North Gujarat, South Gujarat, Saurashtra and Kutch territory. The diverse sorts of commercial enterprises are situated in various regions and zones. Industry bunch shrewd advancement occurred in various zone of the state.

Figure 2-1 DMIC influence zone

The figure above shows the Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor, a regional-level intervention by the central government to promote and facilitate industrial development from Dadri in Uttar Pradesh to Jawaharlal Nehru port in Navi Mumbai. Majority of its influence zone lies within Gujarat from Palanpur in the north to Mehsana to Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Dholera, Bharuch, Surat, Navsari and Valsad in the south. The buffer of 150 kms on either side of the corridor promotes industrial development and encourages establishments of new industrial townships. Special Investment Regions (SIR) like Dholera, Bharuch-Dahej Investment Region, Halol-Savli Industrial areas have benefitted immensely due to the presence of Delhi-Mumbai Industrial Corridor and its policies.

Figure 2-2 Comprehensive Industrial Presence in Gujarat

The figure above shows the cluster of different manufacturing industries in Gujarat. Overall, the presence of industries is quite comprehensive in nature. Either based on existing infrastructure, raw materials, labor or topography, certain kinds of industrial clusters have developed in certain regions, thus forming clusters at a regional-scale. Production of chemicals, petrochemicals, pharmaceuticals, textiles, diamonds is mainly along the DMIC corridor from Ahmedabad till south of Gujarat including Vadodara, Ankleshwar, Surat, Navsari and Valsad. Mehsana has mainly agro-processing and dairy industries, whereas, Morbi, Rajkot and Surendranagar lead in ceramic manufacturing industries. Saurashtra region of Bhavnagar and Amreli have more cement manufacturing and soda-ash industrial clusters than any other place in Gujarat. Jamnagar, Porbandar and Veraval due to their geographical location and natural resources have mainly petroleum and mineral-based industries thriving in this region. Region around Kachchh has many salt manufacturing industries. In nearby port areas, like Kandla and Mundra, industrial clusters producing automotives and engineering equipments are present.

Figure 2-3 Growth Centres & Industrial Estate of Gujarat

2.3 Policies-Past & Present

To promote industrial development and to generate sources of income, as well as create jobs for all, government policies play a major role. Policies include various kinds of laws, incentives, subsidies, ease-to-do business facilities, single window clearances, tax exemptions and so on. These policies also have both-positive and negative externalities in various forms.

2.3.1 National-level

In 1971 central government presented the main impetuses based plan for encouraging mechanical advancement. From that point forward, the measure of incentives and the ranges where they are offered has been always expanding. Amid that time, 80% of the aggregate region of the state was qualified for incentives. Money endowment on altered capital venture and deals charge emption are the significant types of motivating forces that are given.

Figure 2-4 Incentive areas through State Policy in 1997

Industrial sector was among the first to be liberalized in 1991.

New Industrial Policy (NIP) was introduced:

- Key was rapid industrialization of the country.
- To maintain sustain growth in productivity and employment of the country.
- Industrial licensing had been abolished except in a small number of sectors.
- Restriction was removed on expansion.
- Increasing foreign investment and use of foreign technology.

Hence, industries had to register themselves directly with the Registrar of Companies (RoC) under the Ministry of Corporate Affairs.

It was only after 2000, with the agreement of all the state governments that the sales tax incentives were withdrawn. The sales tax being the only tax under the purview of the state government was a favorite tool for the state governments to attract industrialists.

2.3.2 State-level

In Gujarat, chiefly two sorts of impetuses were given, Sales charge exclusion/suspension and Cash appropriations. It was begun in three areas Surendranagar, Bharuch and Panchmahal in 1971. The land scope of the motivators and measure of impetuses has expanded amid consequent approach periods. The most recent period when the impetuses were connected (1995-2000), 144 talukas out of 184 were getting motivating forces in 1995-2000. The motivating forces were stopped after 2000, by the understanding of that request being come to by all the state legislatures of India. The new SEZ approach, however utilizes impetuses as a part of a much or thoroughly.

Gujarat has recorded amazing financial advancement and is the most industrialized condition of India. Taking after the alluring direct motivating forces, Gujarat has seen full hailed modern improvement 1960 onwards. The condition of Gujarat is separated into five zones viz. Focal Gujarat, North Gujarat, South Gujarat, Saurashtra and Kutch range. The distinctive sorts of commercial ventures are situated in various areas and zones. Industry bunch astute advancement occurred in various zone of the state. The examination of the zones regarding rate offer of commercial ventures, speculation and work of the specific zones of the state and as far as Industry Group shrewd units specifically zones.

Some of the main policies and incentives are:

Policy years	Areas covered	Incentives	Special Features
1980-1985	Category A : 7 Districts fully <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Kachch o Junagadh o Amreli o Bhavnagar o Banaskantha o Sabarskantha o Mehsana 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 5% or Rs.5 Lakhs, which ever is less entitled for the subsidy on fix capital investment by state government o 15% or Rs.15 Lakhs, which ever is less entitled for the subsidy on fix capital investment by Central government o Sales tax exemption or deferment scheme for new and existing industries under expansion/diversification 	<p>It was the policy for the industrial development in all districts of the state. Benefits were available to all type of industries, more or less.</p>
	Category B : Talukas eligible for incentives 21 Taluka – Backward More than 30 – Growth Centers 17 Taluka – GIDC Estates		
	Category C : Talukas eligible for at the rate of 50% of state <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Growth centres falling within 24 Km of Municipal Limits of Ahmedabad and Vadodara o Growth centre falling within 10 Km of Municipal limits of Surat,Rajkot,Bhavnagar and Jamnagar 		
1985-1991	Category D : Dang District	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o For small scale industries the contribution of subsidy of state was increased for 10% and in case of large and medium scale industries it was as it is. o Sales tax exemptions or Deferment scheme for new and existing industries under expansion/diversification. o State Government has declared concession equivalent to 10% of the total amount of bills under the heads 'Demand Charges' and 'Energy Charges' as in force from time to time for the first five years for all types of industries. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Government had introduces special scheme for pioneer unites o Small scale industries started by SC/ST/SEBC entrepreneurs or women entrepreneurs could get 5% more subsidy except in the banned area, subject to certain conditions. o Composite sales tax scheme were also introduced o Industries, which provide basic needs and household income in rural area, were not included
	Category B : Except Ineligible areas <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Panchmahals o Surendranagar o Bharuch 		
	Category C : Districts of (Except Ineligible areas) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Bhavnagar o Amreli o Kachch o Sabarkantha o Mehsana o Banaskantha o Junagadh 		
	Category D : At Vapi, only petrochemical and chemical industries were made eligible for incentive under category IV		

Policy years	Areas covered	Incentives	Special Features
1991-1995	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 140 Talukas out of 184 Talukas of the state were made eligible for incentive package. o 8 special backward areas were also made eligible for incentive. o They all were divided into two major categories for availing incentives. o 86 Talukas in category I and 54 Talukas in category II 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The fix capital investment subsidy schemes and sales tax benefit scheme was continued but with changing of covered area. o First time, small sector units have been separated from small-scale industries and were offered incentives at a higher rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o For the first time, incentives were offered for setting up employment intensive industries, prestige's units and 100% export oriented units o Existing units undertaking expansion or diversification were offered incentives at the same rate o The list of ineligible industries had reduced to minimum o The definition of eligible fix capital investment had been widened
1995-2000	<p>All talukas of the district of the state were divided in two categories and in banned areas different incentives for different type of industrial units</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Capital incentive subsidy and sales tax schemes were made limited 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Eligible areas were grouped into two main categories, giving a wider choice of location. o Thrust industries, premier and prestigious units, eligible for incentives all over the state, except in a few banned areas. o Electronic industries eligible to receive capital subsidy (small & tiny) and sales tax incentives (all) throughout the state, including metropolitan cities o Tiny units set up and managed by SC/ST/other backward classes/ women entrepreneurs/ educated unemployed youths offered cash subsidy at a higher rate o Investments in project related infrastructure, made eligible for the purpose of incentives.
2000-2003	<p>All district of the state are covered for different type of industrial development, which is based on trend of the liberalization and globalization</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Concept of capital incentive subsidy has been changed o Sales tax incentive is also abolished as per the guideline of central government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Concept of interest subsidy to small-scale industries is introduced o Incentive for quality certification, interest subsidy to educate unemployed in service sector, infrastructure assistance to medium and large industries, assistance for patent registration etc., is introduced o Concept of employment park, hi-tech park, investment park, and trade center with some special incentive is introduced o Concept or cluster approach, market promotion, technology upgradation, promotion of specific industrial sectors, rehabilitation of sick industrial units, entrepreneurship development, upgradation of GIDC estate, environment protection etc., is introduced

Policy years	Areas covered	Incentives	Special Features
2003-2009	The policy was not area specific , it was more group based than area based.	Capital incentive subsidies have been further reduced .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ More thrust on infrastructure and environment were given ○ Strengthening the existing GIDCs and proposal for new ones ○ Special concerns for MSMEs ○ Special concern for port led and regional development for industrial areas in the state
2009 onwards	The policy did not have any specific incentive on the basis of areas, all the districts had equal advantage of the incentives.	All the incentives were group based , different incentives have been announced depending upon the type of industry.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Concept of SIRs has been given weightage in the policy ○ Enhancement of technical competence and manpower ○ Increasing the efficiency of institutions, catalyzing industrial development ○ Upgrading infrastructure

Figure 2-5 State Policies since 1980's

2.3.2.1 Sales Tax Incentive Scheme

This plan was relevant to all minor, little, medium and extensive scale units in the qualified regions and extraordinary in reverse regions already distinguished. The unit qualified was qualified for exception of offers duty for both buy of crude material and offer of fabricated products. This plan likewise entitled the units exception from turnover expense and focal deals charge.

Figure 2-6 Growth centres in Gujarat (1977)

2.3.2.2 Interest Subsidy to small Scale Industry

Another plan has been presented by give interest sponsorship at the rate of 5% for each annum for a long time period up to a greatest of Rs. 25 lakhs to every single mechanical unit coming up in the state. Existing units completing extension, expansion will be offered

interest appropriation at a rate of 3% for each annum up to a greatest of Rs. 15 lakhs. On the other hand, self-financed units will be endowment at a rate of 10% of repaired capital speculation to a greatest of Rs. 10 lakhs.

Aside from these motivators, the state government plans to take up a bunch based methodology for mechanical improvement. The administration would offer budgetary help up to Rs. 5 crores for improvement of normal offices to the distinguished bunches.

Monetary help would likewise be accommodated quality confirmation up to half of the consumption for affirmation subject to a most extreme point of confinement of Rs. 2 lakhs.

Help to the medium and expansive industry would be given to meet the expense of foundation like area, force association, water offices, environment assurance, development of streets, and so on up to 25% of such cost subject to a greatest of Rs. 100 lakhs. This breaking point can be stretched out up to Rs. 250 lakhs for offices reaching out to provincial regions.

half of the costs for documenting licenses of the exploration by industry and R and D establishments would be conceived by the state government, subject to a most extreme breaking point of Rs.5 lakhs.

The state Government will energize advancement of particular modern segment like agro and nourishment handling businesses, minerals, mineral based commercial ventures, gadgets and data innovation, building subordinate commercial ventures, material commercial ventures, pharmaceuticals and petrochemical downstream and plastic preparing units. The State Govt. has introduced Gujarat Board of Industrial Finance and Reconstruction (GBIFR) in 1998 to **rehabilitate potentially viable small scale industrial units.**

2.3.2.3 Up gradation of GIDC Estates

The mechanical domains set up by Gujarat Industrial Development Corporation (GIDC) will be overhauled. Area will be made accessible at moderate costs to modern units. GIDC advised territories will be given more self-sufficiency and strengthening. The state government would support setting up of mechanical parks through private area venture.

Figure 2-7 Incentive Areas (1986)

2.3.2.4 Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Policy

The Government of India have declared a Policy of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) amid March 2000 with a perspective to expanding framework offices for fare generation. The foundation of first SEZ in the nation has been endorsed in Gujarat under SEZ Policy of GOI. Also, the current Free Trade Zones in particular Kandla Free Trade Zone and Surat Export Processing Zone have been changed over into Special Economic Zones and these are in operation in the State. Also, there are new proposition to set up SEZs in the State.

With regards to Government of India rules for the foundation of SEZs, the matter of planning an arrangement in regards to the allotments which the State Government will accord to advance the improvement of SEZs, the state government has declared a strategy to be connected to all SEZs in the State to be specific Kandla SEZ, Surat SEZ and proposed SEZ at Positra, Mundra and Dahej and at whatever other areas where SEZ may come up in Gujarat, subject to the structure of SEZ controlled by Government of India occasionally. These SEZs are to be esteemed outside region for levy and exchange operations. The state government has appointed every one of the obligations identified with administration of SEZs to assigned advancement chief. He would be giving authorizations for everything identified with the SEZ including Power, Environmental clearances. Water supply frameworks, Labor related reports, and so forth. It would go about as single window leeway for the business visionaries. Aside from that, the units coming up in the zone would be expanded deals charge and different advantages as recorded beneath:

(i) Complete exception on installment of Stamp Duty and Registration Fees on exchange of area implied for mechanical use in the SEZ Area.

(ii) Complete exclusion on installment of stamp obligation and enrollment charge for advance understandings, credit deeds, contracts and so on relating to SEZ units or which will be executed inside of the SEZ zone.

(iii) Transactions inside of the SEZ might be exempted from all State charges including Sales Tax, VAT, Motor soul charge, extravagance expense and amusement charge, buy charge and other state charges.

(iv) Inputs (merchandise and administrations) made to SEZ units from Domestic Tariff Area (DTA) will be excluded from Sales charge and other State charges.

(v) Any deals from SEZ to DTA will be dealt with as import and import obligation will be appropriate according to GOI strategy. Deals duty will be relevant to SEZ merchandise as

appropriate to other imported products. Same Rules and Procedure will be appropriate to SEZ products as pertinent to typical imports.

(vi) Due to duty framework imperatives, in the event that it is unrealistic to give direct exception to any exchanges, such installment of State assessments will be repaid to the SEZ units.

(vii) The SEZ engineer and SEZ units will be qualified to benefit exception under (a) to (f) above amid execution period also.

2.3.2.5 Infrastructure - Financial Assistance to Industrial Parks

Gujarat Industrial Policy - 2003 has recognized framework advancement as a need on the state plan. Setting up of Industrial Park is as vital foundation for commercial ventures. The State Government is empowering interest of private area for setting up little domains and particular Industrial Parks. A different plan was presented under Gujarat Industrial Policy 2000 and has discovered support. In this manner, the State Government has likewise turned out with a plan to urge private part engineers to set up Special Economic Zones and Industrial Parks. The new modern arrangement underscores at proceeding with the monetary help for hey tech parks, speculation parks, send out parks and so on. Administration of Gujarat has hence, presented an altered plan in such manner.

The Developer of the industrial park will be eligible for exemption on payment of **stamp duty** on purchase of land. However, the industrial units in the park will be required to pay **stamp duty** at the rate of 50% of duty.

2.3.2.6 Infrastructure - Critical Infrastructure Projects

The State Government has presented a few plans towards foundation improvement including setting up of Industrial Parks, up gradation of framework offices in modern bequests other than advancement of base office for industry.

Advantages

50 % of the task cost up to a greatest of Rs. 5 crore.

Qualified Criteria

Any of the accompanying tasks are qualified for help :

- (i) Approach street from modern domain/territory to airplane terminal, port or expressway
- (ii) Over bridge on street/railroad.
- (iii) Up gradation of existing streets/enlarging of street.
- (iv) Construction of by pass street
- (v) Setting up of earth station/correspondence offices
- (vi) Water dissemination organize and related offices
- (vii) Gas/Electricity/Energy circulation arrange and related offices
- (viii) Any other framework office required in the range particular to industry.
- (ix) Setting up of product lodging offices and related offices.

(x) Facilitation Center, Product Development Center, Training Center, Testing Center, R and D Institution and/or any Common Facility Center.

The legislature would likewise give a money sponsorship of 25% of the speculation for Common Effluent Treatment Plants (CETPs) for natural security.

The Government has familiar an arrangement with give assistance towards the cost of establishment like territory cost (numbering legal and trade charge), power transmission line, improvement of procedure road (associated with state roadway, national avenue, MDR/ODR et cetera) by medium and considerable present day endeavors coming up in nation regions.

Advantages

Qualified unit will be given money related help at the rate of 25% upto a most extreme of Rs.100 lakh, If the undertaking has country linkage it will be given budgetary help at the rate of 25% upto a greatest of Rs.250 lakh.

2.3.2.7 Cluster Development

The Government has acquainted a plan with give help towards the expense of foundation like area expense (counting lawful and exchange charge), power transmission line, development of methodology street (connected with state roadway, national thruway, MDR/ODR and so forth) by medium and substantial modern undertakings coming up in country territories.

2.3.2.8 DMIC and the influence area in Gujarat

The State Government has wanted to create Ahmedabad - Dholera Special Investment Region (SIR), Petroleum, Chemical and Petrochemical Investment Region (PCPIR), Gujarat International Finance Tech City (GIFT), Knowledge Corridor and Integrated

Townships. The State Government means to proactively grow universally benchmarked foundation in every one of these locales.

Social and Urban Infrastructure is critical to maintain mechanical improvement. The State Government plans to support interest in social and urban framework areas in the Investment Regions, Hubs and Industrial Parks. There will be linkages between mechanical base and social and urban base in the region of modern region to make accessible urban base and enhance personal satisfaction of the general population.

High effect/market driven hubs - Integrated Investment Regions (IRs) and Industrial Areas (IAs) have been recognized along the Delhi Mumbai Industrial Corridor to give straightforward and venture inviting office administrations. These locales are proposed to act naturally supported mechanical townships with world-class base, street and rail network for cargo development to and from ports and logistic centers, served by local/universal air availability, solid force, quality social base to give an all inclusive aggressive environment helpful for setting up organizations.

2.3.2.9 Facilitation to Mega Projects

The GoG expects to advance and encourage uber ventures in a couple of basic segments which would have multiplier impact and would be indispensable to the job era movement and comprehensive improvement in the state. Substantial and Mega ventures advance subordinate and helper commercial ventures in the SME segment.

The units having venture of Rs 1000 crore and vocation of 2000 will be characterized as Mega Units. Though in Core Infrastructure Sector, the units having venture of Rs. 5000 crore will be dealt with as Mega Units.

The state government may likewise order GIDC to catalyze Mega Projects in different districts where the advancement of part particular super ventures would be taken up.

- Region particular motivating forces were not advanced in the later approaches, in light of the fact that in spite of giving colossal impetuses to districts of Dangs, Panchmahal, Kachchh and so on no improvement was going on in these locale and thus in later years it was made open for real part of the state
- Throughout every one of the strategies, every one of the sorts of commercial ventures i. e. minor ,little, medium vast and so on have been given equivalent weight age for impetuses and all have been advanced
- Special push has been given to various gatherings of commercial enterprises in various years, similar to gadgets and compound businesses were given exceptional motivations in 90's, IT based and benefit commercial ventures have been given unique motivators post 2000e and so forth.
- Infrastructure up degree, human asset advancement, market advancement, environment security and so forth have been a necessary part of the strategies since 2000
- Home based commercial ventures have been totally overlooked however out every one of the arrangements
- Monitory motivators as far as capital sponsorship, deals charge exclusions were an essential part of the prior approaches however once the modern development got steady and smooth gradually and gradually they were lessened in the later strategies
- Over all, every one of the strategies have been fruitful in pulling in the mechanical interests in the state and gave a steady and smooth environment for the modern business people
- Kachchh, in spite of being considered as one of the regressive locale of Gujarat and over and again being given major monetary preferences, no significant speculations happened there until the declaration of "Impetus Scheme 2001 for Economic Development of Kachchh District"

2.4 Use of Open Data

The growth of open data is shifting the emphasis from longer term strategic planning to short-term thinking about how cities function and can be managed. Open data holds the promise of a rich, detailed and timely data that can provide a better understanding of complex problems of the world we live in. Computations and interrelations between multiple sectorial data facilitate planners to analyze and provide better urban planning solutions.

However, the access to open data in India is highly limited, since privately owned businesses and government generate most of that data. And where access is gained, a number of security and ethical challenges of using such highly resolute data props up. Open data has the potential to become a good governance strategy. It can be integrated into the administrative system of the government, especially if it becomes a public engagement mechanism. It can encourage political openness and bring about broader legal reforms and transparency, thereby strengthening the democratic freedom of citizens. Somehow, these aspects that are ideals of open data are less focused on. Community consultations and communication between different stakeholders will benefit from the availability of open data in terms of planning decisions. The digitized version of data will be foolproof data without human intervention, thus reducing corrupt practices and encouraging urban voices in decision-making. Democratizing urban planning processes is a task in itself since there are multiple stakeholders involved, but with open data we can strengthen the democratic passions within us because of its universal availability, access through social media applications and manifestation of our suggestions.

If open data is embedded into cities strategic activities, its applications can become more sustainable. Many decision-making and planning processes in councils, local governments and organizations can be based on both real-time and historical data. In coming times, open data will produce significant results and create tangible impacts in the field of urban planning, decision-making and governance.

SOURCE: McKinsey Global Institute analysis

Figure 2-8 Kinds of Data

Open data is an element of government record keeping, data administration, shared administrations and national spatial information foundations and not simply a standalone program. Open data is also no guarantee of a more evidence-informed, deliberative and engaged society unless there are broader legal reforms, political openness, transparency, education, capacity building, a critically numerate journalism, polity and society, and the welcoming of real and meaningful citizen engagement. Most of the data for cities are invariably tagged to space and time. The growth of open data is shifting the emphasis from longer term strategic planning to short-term thinking about how cities function and can be managed. Data without theory is meaningless, however one can argue that we can now forget theory in the age of open data. All one needs to look for in open data are more and more correlations. Such data are potentially extremely useful for figuring out disruptions in the system and can prove an effective tool for urban planning.

Implications on Urban Planning

In the history of urban studies and planning, most theory and applications have focused on the long term – on what happens in cities measured over months and years, certainly not over minutes and hours. In fact, transport has always been concerned with peak daily flows, but these are assumed to pertain to a much longer period and thus most of our theory and planning has been focused on what happens to cities over planning horizons that relate to years- the short terms being 5 years and the long term 20 or 50 years. Much of the routine management of cities has been accomplished in ad hoc ways, not necessarily without any data or science but certainly without the kind of comprehensive theory and modeling that characterizes the long term. Smart cities believe a shift in this emphasis to a deeper understanding of how urban systems function in the short term (Davies, 2014).

Cities have economic, social and environmental attributes besides spatial and temporal dimensions. Urban planning has to address these factors. So, economic, social and environmental information should be added on the spatial-temporal information model. Urban planning needs to access and consume a large amount of data. Planning related information consist of 2D map, 3D urban model, thematic information, historical data, national statistics, local survey, and various policy and regulations, etc. Planners need to access data sources individually and then combine the results manually every time. This is a very tedious and time-consuming task. The cost of gathering and processing this data is arguably the most significant cost for planning analysis. Effective decision support depends on the integrity and reliability of the information and knowledge available to decision-makers. Therefore, an integrated information model is needed in support of urban planning (Kitchin, 2013).

Open Data aims to produce integrated and interoperable city systems. This entails the extra task of database maintenance, for data consistency and integrity. When sustainability and quality of urban life is generally considered, a more holistic analysis of city issues during the planning process is needed. It calls for city models to be based on integrated data sets. Visualization can aid the communication and collaboration among many participants during the problem solving and decision making of urban planning

(Langendorf, 2001). The design solutions to planning problems deal not only simply with present data but also with past and future data (Harris and Batty, 1993). It will facilitate data collection, documentation, access, exchange and transfer at urban scale, through both spatial and thematic data.

Data sources that have to be integrated do not always reside on the same place. It's likely to be that they are on different hardware platforms and operating systems and across different organizations and agencies. Planner may not have administrative control over them, cannot modify their structure, or write data to them. How to communicate between the dispersive data sources is an issue that need to be addressed when creating an integrated system and choosing the appropriate architecture. However, no solution is perfect and can solve all problems. By using IT, data can be collected relevant to different city issues and integrated together for later use in city planning. It is also important to understand how data sets can be integrated at different scales by developing urban database at the urban scale. We should be able to build interoperable database that can seamlessly integrate various urban datasets and support computer and human decision making to enhance the management of cities.

If open data is embedded into cities strategic activities, applications can be sustainable. Many decision-making and planning processes in councils, local governments and organizations are based on both real-time and historical data. In coming times, open data will produce significant results and create tangible impacts in the field of urban planning, decision-making and governance.

CHAPTER 3
SPATIO-TEMPORAL ANALYSIS

3. Spatio-temporal Analysis

To understand the evolution of manufacturing industries in Gujarat since 1991, it is important to identify spatial locations of these industries over the period of time.

3.1 Open Governmental Data

Apart from the Registrar of Companies (RoC) data which shall be primarily analyzed, certain key datasets will be used for this research. They include data from Annual Survey of Industries, Commissionerate of Industries, Census and such other economic data.

3.1.1 Ministry of Corporate Affairs & Registrar of Companies

Through the open data source data.gov.in, large databases are available from Ministry of Corporate Affairs, released under National Data Sharing and Accessibility Policy (NDSAP). Companies that are registered with the Registrar of Companies (RoC) are either companies listed by shares/guarantee or unlisted companies. One such dataset is being used for this research which includes all registered manufacturing industries in Gujarat.

3.1.2 Selection Criteria - Based on type, time and location

Out of the 81000 registered companies in Gujarat with Registrar of Companies (as of 31.03.2015), more than 34000 are manufacturing industries of food, leather products, machinery and equipment, metal and chemicals, paper, textiles and wood products. These manufacturing industries are being considered for this study.

Table 1: Classification of Manufacturing Industries in Gujarat

Type of Industry	Number of Industries
Metal & Chemical	14027
Textiles	7526
Machinery & Equipment	7203
Food Based	2315
Paper Based	1193
Wood Based	400
Leather Based	76
Others	1776
TOTAL	34509

Table 2: Raw Data Sheet from Registrar of Companies

CORPORATE ID	YEAR OF REGISTRATION	COMPANY NAME	COMPANY STATUS	COMPANY CLASS	COMPANY CATEGORY	AUTHORIZED CAPITAL	PAIDUP CAPITAL	REGISTERED STATE	REGISTRAR DISTRICT	PRINCIPAL ACTIVITY	REGISTERED ADDRESS	SUB CATEGORY	LATITUDE	LONGITUDE
U24233GJ2014PT	2014	GENERAL MOTOR	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	96500000000	65871693600	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	101 KALING, NR.	Indian_NonGove	23.031739	72.570458
U17200GJ2014PT	2014	IDEA CELLULAR L	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	82750000000	35978444300	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	GANDHINAGAR C	Indian_NonGove	23.215635	72.636941
U36911GJ1994PT	1994	ONGC PETRO ADI	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	80000000000	20219296700	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	1st FLOOR, OMK	Indian_NonGove	22.278973	73.185112
L34100GJ1985PL	1985	ESSAR STEEL IND	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	72750000000	29307936700	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	27km,SURAT HAZ	Subsidiary_of_Fo	21.186944	72.759514
U17200GJ1947PT	1947	ESSAR STEEL (HA	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	60000000000	30568591300	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	POST HAZIRA, DIS	Subsidiary_of_Fo	21.117004	72.644683
U18102GJ1985PL	1985	BHANDER POWE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	50000000000	3784525000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	27th KM, SURAT	Indian_NonGove	21.186944	72.759514
U18102GJ1985PL	1985	ESSAR POWER (O	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	50000000000	3591400000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	27th Km, Surat -	Indian_NonGove	21.186944	72.759514
U36939GJ1991PT	1991	VADINAR OIL TER	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	40000000000	10461420000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	Essar Refinery Sit	Indian_NonGove	22.205260	69.658776
U32100GJ1997PT	1997	RELIANCE PETRO	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	30000000000	500000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	VILLAGE MOTIKH	Indian_NonGove	22.396900	69.824003
U17120GJ2008PT	2008	VODAFONE WEST	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	27500000000	5000000000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	6TH FLOOR SAKA	Indian_NonGove	23.023111	72.572523
U26109GJ1985PT	1985	HAZIRA PLATE LIM	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	20000000000	8004672340	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	27 KM SURAT HA	Indian_NonGove	21.186944	72.759514
U24100GJ2012PT	2012	TORRENT POWER	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	20000000000	4724483080	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	TORRENT HOUSE	Indian_NonGove	23.066843	72.586480
U25199GJ1996PT	1996	INDIAN PETROCH	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	16000000000	3007027980	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	P.O. PETROCHEM	Indian_NonGove	22.307159	73.181219
U17116GJ1990PT	1990	JHAGADIA COPPE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	15000000000	7862510310	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	PLOT NO 747 GID	Indian_NonGove	21.677502	73.205760
U29259GJ2013PT	2013	JSW STEEL (SALA	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	15000000000	9337109580	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	Welspun City, Vill	Indian_NonGove	23.119288	70.036265
U17116GJ1990PT	1990	GSPC LNG LIMITE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	10000000000	1546300600	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	GSPC BHAVAN, B	State_Governme	21.673288	72.999201
U17119GJ1997PT	1997	ASIA KUNSTSTOF	DORMANT	Private	Company_Limited	10000000000	200	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	VRAJ SHANTI 63,	Indian_NonGove	22.313295	73.176588
U15209GJ2002PT	2002	PRINCE PAPER M	UNDER_PROCESS	Private	Company_Limited	10000000000	200	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Paper_Based	PLOT NO.412/2,C	Indian_NonGove	20.599235	72.934245
U15400GJ2011PT	2011	PIPAVAV DEFENC	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	10000000000	7362062690	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	Pipavav Shipyard	Indian_NonGove	21.048045	71.429936
U17120GJ2013PT	2013	APCO INDUSTRIE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	10000000000	33131000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	1967/1968 VILLA	Indian_NonGove	23.243004	72.437650
U24132GJ2015PT	2015	CHINA STEEL CO	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	79000000000	7286905600	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	PLOT NO.7, STRE	Indian_NonGove	22.216963	70.752530
U24120GJ2011PT	2011	ARVIND LIMITED	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	66500000000	2582430690	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Textiles	NARODA ROAD A	Indian_NonGove	23.048949	72.622662
U34300GJ1998PT	1998	P B SUTARIA MA	UNDER_PROCESS	Public	Company_Limited	65000000000	6500000000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	NR BRAHMAKSH	Indian_NonGove	22.470702	70.057730
U18109GJ2014PT	2014	AMBUJA CEMENT	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	65000000000	3099976170	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	113/40, SARABH	Indian_NonGove	23.031934	72.587850
U29100GJ2010PT	2010	SIDDHI VINAYAK	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	60000000000	4000000000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	NIRMA HOUSE, A	Indian_NonGove	23.031739	72.570458
U17100GJ2010PT	2010	SE FORGE LIMITE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	52500000000	4162541250	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	5, SHRIMALI SOC	Indian_NonGove	23.034871	72.566396
U31909GJ1988PT	1988	JK PAPER LIMITE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	50000000000	1366206250	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Paper_Based	P.O. Central Pulp	Indian_NonGove	21.211150	73.565302
U17119GJ1989PT	1989	HAZIRA PIPE MIL	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	50000000000	2057531330	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	27 K.M. SURAT H	Indian_NonGove	21.217647	72.799803
U15400GJ2008PT	2008	GUJARAT SIDHEE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	50000000000	361538520	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	SIDHEEGRAM VEI	Indian_NonGove	20.785083	70.633576
U17119GJ1993PT	1993	SABIC RESEARCH	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	45000000000	3152599100	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Textiles	PLOT NO. 5 & 6,S	Indian_NonGove	22.258652	71.192381
U15140GJ1994PT	1994	UPL LIMITED	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	40000000000	857208548	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	3-11, G.I.D.C., VA	Indian_NonGove	20.365284	72.951224
U24219GJ2000PT	2000	HIGHLY ELECTRIC	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	39000000000	2118473350	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	Survey No.456,45	Subsidiary_of_Fo	22.917969	72.413979
U29100GJ2008PT	2008	MAXXIS RUBBER	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	37000000000	3700000000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	A/1, 2nd Floor, S	Subsidiary_of_Fo	23.024349	72.530152
U30009GJ1997PT	1997	RECRON SYNTHE	AMALGAMATED	Public	Company_Limited	35000000000	2955801110	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Textiles	402/B 4TH FLOOR	Indian_NonGove	22.321808	73.166978
U33111GJ2014PT	2014	NEXANS INDIA PR	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	32000000000	1500000000	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	VEJALPUR ROAD,	Indian_NonGove	22.774346	73.601880
U26921GJ1995PL	1995	SUN PHARMACEL	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	30000000000	2071163910	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	SPARC TANDALJA	Indian_NonGove	22.300824	73.173313
U29199GJ1998PT	1998	WARM STREAM T	STRIKE_OFF	Private	Company_Limited	30000000000	0	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	ANAND SOJITRA	Indian_NonGove	22.539917	72.909098
U17120GJ2009PT	2009	GUJARAT STATE F	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	30000000000	2524486490	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	GSPC BHWAN, BE	State_Governme	23.027461	72.584489
U15142GJ2009PT	2009	MADURA GARME	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	28000000000	1088888900	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Textiles	n Rayon Compou	Indian_NonGove	20.915898	70.362852
U35117GJ2008PT	2008	GPT STEEL INDUS	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	25500000000	2522755070	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	102 Dev Shruti C	Indian_NonGove	23.026233	72.562312
U29259GJ1989PT	1989	SUSABH FASHION	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	25100000000	2036270	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Textiles	BLOCK NO 73 PLC	Indian_NonGove	21.257072	73.303071
U24231GJ1987PT	1987	SHAKUNTALA DY	STRIKE_OFF	Private	Company_Limited	25000000000	0	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Paper_Based	41,SUGAM SOCIE	Indian_NonGove	21.198951	72.806237
U29192GJ1990PT	1990	GUJARAT NARMA	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	25000000000	1554187830	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	P.O. Narmadanag	Indian_NonGove	21.745035	73.022817
U17100GJ1997PT	1997	SHREE DIGVIJAY	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	25000000000	1413742780	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	POST-DIGVIJAY G	Indian_NonGove	22.396900	69.824003
U24111GJ2003PT	2003	D.B. CORP LIMITE	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	25000000000	1836492580	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Paper_Based	PLOT NO. 280, SA	Indian_NonGove	22.996040	72.499670
U15132GJ2006PT	2006	MANGAL RUBBER	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	25000000000	2277200	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	PLOT NO.308-309	Indian_NonGove	20.673213	72.981488
U17200GJ2013PT	2013	WELSPUN CORP	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	25000000000	1314741500	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	Welspun City, Vill	Indian_NonGove	23.119288	70.036265
U18101GJ1998PT	1998	ITT CORPORATIO	ACTIVE	Private	Company_Limited	24100000000	2049351790	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Machinery & Equ	Plot No. 731, Ma	Subsidiary_of_Fo	22.437457	73.196972
U24231GJ1997PT	1997	SHRENO LIMITED	ACTIVE	Public	Company_Limited	24000000000	660498240	Gujarat	RoC-Ahmedabad	Metals_Chemical	ALEMBIC ROAD V	Indian_NonGove	22.323552	73.166211

3.2 Spatio-temporal Analysis

3.2.1 Gujarat

The Registrar of Companies (RoC) data is used to generate manufacturing industries maps based on the following:

1. Time

Every year, many industries register themselves with RoC, and hence this can be included to carry out research based on time. This is an essential component of spatio-temporal analysis.

2. Type

There are various kinds of manufacturing industries considered for this study: Metal & Chemicals, Textiles, Machinery & Equipments, Food-based, Paper-based, Wood, Leather and Others. These manufacturing industries are classified as industries with primary principal activity and thus can be used to understand industrial growth in the state.

3. Status (Active/Dormant)

It is important to understand that which industries are active and which are not active, where have industries flourished more and in which areas have industries shut down.

4. Category (Listed by Shares/Guarantee or Unlisted)

To know the category of industries, i.e, large-scale, medium-scale and small-scale industries and their capital/revenue, categorization and scale of employment is also important.

5. Class (Public/Private)

There are two categories: Public and Private, based on which spatio-temporal analysis can be done. Relating the growth of private industries with governmental policies will help us understand the growth pattern and market potential.

Figure 3-1 Decadal Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Gujarat

The growth of manufacturing industries in Gujarat shows that various policies, incentives, infrastructure facilities, and certain other factors have triggered growth in the state since 1981 onwards. Mainly, after 1991 liberalization of the Indian economy, manufacturing industries of metals, chemicals, machinery and equipments have thrived. The absolute numbers of textile industries have remained stagnant but they are in large numbers. Gujarat being one of the highly industrialized states in India has constant industrial growth rate which is reflected in the graph below.

Figure 3-2 Growth Trends of Manufacturing Industries in Gujarat

Figure 3-3 Spatial Locations of Manufacturing Industries (by years)

Figure 3-4 Spatial Locations of Manufacturing Industries (by type)

Figure 3-5 Spatial Locations of Manufacturing Industries (by category)

Figure 3-6 Spatial Locations of Manufacturing Industries (by status)

Figure 3-7 Spatial Locations of Manufacturing Industries (by class)

Figure 3-8 Spatial Locations of Metal & Chemical Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-9 Spatial Locations of Textiles Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-10 Spatial Locations of Machinery & Equipments Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-11 Spatial Locations of Food-based Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-12 Spatial Locations of Wood-based Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-13 Spatial Location of Leather-based Manufacturing Industries

Figure 3-14 Spatial Locations of Other Manufacturing Industries

3.2.2 Five highly industrialized districts

The five highly industrialized districts of Gujarat are selected for the purpose of analysis to understand the evolution over the period of space and time. These five districts are namely: Ahmedabad, Surat, Vadodara, Rajkot and Surendranagar. More than 75% of industries are located in these districts. Hence, analysis of these five districts will lead to a better understanding and co-relating it with various industrial policies of the state and national government will reflect whether the policies are in tune with actual growth.

Trends for top five industrialized districts are done to identify growth pattern of manufacturing industries:

Figure 3-15 Growth Trends of Manufacturing Industries of Gujarat and five highly industrialized districts (based on type)

3.2.2.1 Ahmedabad

Figure 3-16 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Ahmedabad

Though considered Manchester of East, growth of manufacturing industries in Ahmedabad district gathered momentum only after 1996. Talukas located in Ahmedabad district other than Ahmedabad, contributed in the setting up of new manufacturing industries, thus making Ahmedabad the most Industrialized district of Gujarat. Predominantly, metals, chemicals and machinery manufacturing industries are located in this district. It is seen from the graphs that industries have primarily clustered around Ahmedabad taluka, predominantly because of the available infrastructure, road connectivity, human resource and logistics in Ahmedabad city and its vicinity.

Figure 3-17 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Ahmedabad

3.2.2.2 Surat

Figure 3-18 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Surat

In Surat district, growth of manufacturing industries was rapid since Independence and was rapid in the early 1980s and later became stagnant since 1990s. Predominantly, textiles and metals, chemicals industries are located in this district. With the decline of textile industries in Surat district, there was a strong decline in the overall manufacturing industries in Surat district. Also due to the presence of different ports and strategic points near Surat city and taluka, several GIDCs and SIRs were proposed which triggered industrial development in the district. Even in the case of Surat, the industries were concentrated in the city and its surrounding primarily because of the cluster development and available infrastructure, along with labor and cheap raw materials. This reflects, how markets are concentrated around the metropolitan cities, in this case Surat.

Figure 3-19 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Surat

3.2.2.3 Vadodara

Figure 3-20 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Vadodara

In Vadodara district, growth of manufacturing industries gathered momentum in the early 1990s and later became stagnant exponentially. Predominantly, metals, chemicals and machinery manufacturing industries are located in this district. 1991 onwards, there is a kink in the manufacturing industries in Vadodara district. Growth of manufacturing industries became stagnant post 2001. Halol-Savli industrial area was one of the key growth center in terms of industrial development in Vadodara district.

Figure 3-21 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Vadodara

3.2.2.4 Rajkot

Figure 3-22 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Rajkot

In Rajkot district, growth of manufacturing industries was slow in the late 1980s, went up in the early 1990s and later became stagnant exponentially. Predominantly, metals, chemicals and machinery manufacturing industries are located in this district. However, post 1996, Morbi taluka in this district also attracted many manufacturing industries of metals, chemicals, cement and tiles and eventually became a cluster. Rajkot has many metal and chemicals manufacturing industries alongside industries which manufacture machinery and equipments. It is one of the highly industrialized districts which has polycentric development of manufacturing industries due to various reasons like available natural resources, infrastructure and connectivity along with skilled labor force.

Figure 3-23 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Rajkot

3.2.2.5 Surendranagar

Figure 3-24 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Surendranagar

In Surendranagar district, growth of manufacturing industries was rapid in the early 1990s and later became stagnant exponentially. Predominantly, metals, chemicals and machinery manufacturing industries are located in this district. The high kink experienced in 1991 was because of the incentives by state government to promote manufacturing industries in backwards districts, one of them being Surendranagar. To an extent the policies had an impact initially, but later due to the presence of Ahmedabad district in close vicinity, cluster development and new industries were set up in Ahmedabad district.

Figure 3-25 Growth of Manufacturing Industries in Surendranagar

CHAPTER 4

SYNTHESIS

4. Synthesis

4.1 Findings from the analysis

Through spatio-temporal analysis, there are few important findings, as follows:

Policy years	Unique Features	What worked?	What did not work?
1980-1985	Sales tax exemption, subsidies, tax incentives for backward talukas	Gujarat had grown a decade old, so it was necessary to trigger industrial development without regional disparity	Benefits were not available to all kind of industries, rather they were available to a selected few
1985-1991	Subsidies and concession on bills for all types of industries	Encouraging women entrepreneurs and composite sales tax scheme for all types of industries worked in favor	Too much of concentration on backward talukas and losing out on tapping full potential of emerging growth centres around Surat, Rajkot and Ahmedabad
1991-1995	Small sector units offered more incentives to generate employment at grass-root level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post-liberalization of Indian economy, incentives were availed to more than 140 talukas. So, the outreach was widened. • Concentration on exported oriented units. 	Lack of incentives for medium and large-scale industries

1995-2000	Investments in project related infrastructure	Tiny units managed by unemployed youths were offered cash subsidy at a higher rate	Lack of incentives for medium and large-scale industries
2000-2003	Capital incentive subsidy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Concentration of industries (Cluster development) • Technology upgradation and adopting globalization 	Sales tax incentive abolished as per the guidelines of Central government
2003-2009	Concentration on port led and regional industrial development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Policy was group based rather than area based. • Strengthening the GIDCs • More thrust in infrastructure and environment 	Private industries come up near large metropolises like Ahmedabad, Surat, Vadodara which creates regional disparity and concentration of industries
2009 onwards	incentives were group based, depending on industry-type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancement of technical competence and manpower • SIRs given weightage 	

- Despite liberalization of Indian economy in the early 1990s, concentration of manufacturing industries took place near large metropolises.
- The notion of decentralization of new industries and spreading of industries across various talukas of Gujarat hasn't achieved much of a success.
- Out of the 248 talukas in Gujarat, more than 66% of manufacturing industries are located in 3 talukas: Ahmedabad, Vadodara, Surat, thus reflecting the concentration of industries near market and metropolis.
- This also shows that other factors like Delhi Mumbai Industrial Corridor (DMIC), Dedicated Freight Corridor (DFC), National Highway-8, and locations of SIRs, SEZs, GIDCs have played a major role in concentrating manufacturing industries along Ahmedabad-Vadodara-Surat corridor.
- The graph showing the growth of manufacturing industries in Gujarat is an S-curve, thereby showing a rapid, exponential increase of manufacturing industries post-liberalization from 1991-1995 and 1996-2000, later due to state policies and promotion of industries from 2001-2005 and 2006-2010, followed by a tapering/leveling-off from 2011 onwards.

4.2 Way forward

In this case, using open governmental data, we can see the wide gap between policies of the government and on-ground scenario of manufacturing industries established over the period of time. Through the use of similar open data, spatial growth patterns of various sectors can be identified and analyzing the policy interventions can be done for better decision-making to take place. In coming times, open data will produce significant results and create tangible impacts in the field of urban planning, decision-making and governance.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

BOOKS

Amita, S. (July 2001). *Linking Industrial Growth with Rural Economy: A Case Study of Ankleshwar Industrial Estate in Gujarat*. Ahmedabad: Gujarat Institute of Development Research.

Badri, Masood A., (2007) “Dimensions of Industrial location Factors – Review and Explanation”, United Arab Emirates University

Bhaduri, A. (2007). Alternatives Industrialisation. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 2000.

Blair, John P., (1987) ‘Major Factors in Industrial Location – A review’, Wright State University

Dinesh Awasthi, (2001). *Recent Changes in Industrial Economy of Gujarat*

Estall, R. C. and Buchman R. O ‘Industrial Activity and Economic Geography’

Gupta .G, What Are the Factors Responsible for the Localization of Industries?

H. M. Shivanand Swamy, K. Mukundan. *Gujarat - Urban Development Dynamics*.

Hirway, I. (1995). Selected Development and widening disparities in Gujarat. *Economic and Political weekly*.

Hirway, I and Shah, A. (1998). *Liberlisation, Globalisation and Industrialisation: Conflict and Resolution in Regional Context*.

Hirway, I. (1999). *Human Development Report- Gujarat*.

Hirway, I. (October 1999). *Dynamics of Development in Gujarat: Some Issues*. Ahmedabad: CENTRE FOR DEVELOPMENT ALTERNATIVES.

HUBERT SCHMITZ, K. N. (1999). Clustering and Industrialization. *World Development*

Kaplinsky Raphael. *Globalisation, Industrialisation and Sustainable Growth: The Pursuit of the Nth Rent.* IDS Discussion Paper .

Kathuria, Vinish, (2005) “Spatial Location of Industries – Factors Influencing Locational Choice”, *Economic Growth and Development, Second Annual Conference*, Indian Statistical Institute, New Delhi

Keshab, D. (July 2005). *Industrial Clusters in India: Perspectives and Issues for Research.* Ahmedabad: Gujarat Institute of Development Research.

Kevin M. Murphy, A. S. (October 1989). Industrialization and the big push. *The journal of political Economy* , 97, 1003-1026.

Kirit, P. (May 1996). Equitable Sustainable Development of Gujarat. *Economic and Poitical Weekly* , 1151- 1164.

Manoj Modiyani, R. P. (2003). *Process of Industrialization in India.* Anand, Gujarat.

Menon, S. V. (2008). *Drivers of economic growth in Gujarat.* Munich Personal RePEc Archive.

Raju, K. (2009). *Growing rural-urban Disparities in Gujarat.* NIRD.

Smith, David M. (1970), ‘Industrial Location – An Economic Geographical Analysis’, University of Florida

Thaker H. Hrima, S. L. (2009). socio-economic development in gujarat: rosy picture with concerns. *Journal of Rural Development* , 28, 515-528.

Webber, Michale J. ‘Industrial Location –Scientific Geography

UNPUBLISHED THESIS

Bhavsar, Krupal, (2006) “Measuring Effectiveness of tax incentives for Industrial Development – A case of Gujarat”, Postgraduate dissertation, School of Planning, CEPT, Ahmedabad

Dalwadi, A. (2010) “Industrial Development in Gujarat: Comparative Study of Location Factors of Halol-Savli Area”

Pathak, D, (2003) “Trend of Industrialization in Backward Area – A case study of Halol – Kalol”, Postgraduate dissertation, School of Planning, CEPT, Ahmedabad